

Effect of gamma irradiation on structural properties of CrFe₂O₄ ferrite

E. Nagaraja, A S Jagadisha, and H S Jayanna*

Department of Physics, Kuvempu University, Shankaraghatta, Karnataka, India-577 451.

*email: jayanna60@gmail.com, Mobile No: 9844176404

Abstract:

CrFe₂O₄ ferrite was prepared by citrate precursor method. Structural properties were determined by X-ray diffraction. Surface morphological and elemental compositions of the prepared samples were studied by high resolution scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). The prepared samples were irradiated to high energy gamma radiation of ⁶⁰Co source with a dose rate of 6.972 kGy/hr to different doses of 300kGy and 500kGy. The XRD spectra were obtained for the irradiated samples and compared with that of the pristine samples to study the changes in the structure. The obtained results showed that the crystallite size decreases and lattice strain increases with increase of radiation dose.

Key words: chromium ferrite, gamma irradiation, structural changes